

Role of employee's workplace safety towards job performance

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Abstract

This research study looks at the role of employee's workplace safety towards job performance. For this study, 106 different peoples from different places were asked questions about workplace safety and job performance. When the surveys were completed and returned, the data was entered into SPSS for analysis. Several tests like correlation and regression analysis were run on the data, and significant findings were present. I found that there is a positive affect between two variables. I also found, that workplace safety is working properly in some organizations and many industries shows interest in the safety of employees. The results and data are discussed in depth within this report.

Keywords: Employee's workplace, Safety, Job Performance

Introduction:

Safety plays a very important role in the performance of the employees. Danger of workplace can be measured in term of injuries that can be occurred during the work. Over many years ago the rate of such injuries was very high, but with the passage of time the rate of injuries decreases by the using of preventive measures. These injuries are reduced from time to time due to the improvement in the workplace safety.

Employers have the responsibility to provide the safer workplace for which the employees can work easily and effectively to achieve the tasks. It is important for the business success that the employer and employee act fairly. Employers or his representatives have the duty to consult with the employees regarding the health and safety related policies within workplace. Safety department should be working in every organization for the safety of employees and define the safety policies and implementing those policies. Being an employee you have the right to protect ourselves against safety on the jobs. Employees can participate in the policy making because they know better which types of problem they faced during the work. Employees have the right to refuse to do work if the safety at work is not existed. Accidents are the part of the workplace but we can minimize it by adopting safety policies and practices. Employers provide the safety to the employees on the workplace for doing the better work because employees major part of our daily life on working.

The main purpose of this study is to examine the role of employee's workplace safety and how employees workplace safety effect on the job performance. The major direction of this study is to check and evaluate those factors that help in the improvement of job performance.

The second part of the research is to collect the data from different footwear manufacturing industries to identify the effect of job performance of employees in manufacturing sector. The main objectives of this study is to determine the role of workplace safety and to determine the effect of

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workplace safety towards employees job performance

My study will be beneficial for the industrial managers as well as the employers of the plastic footwear manufacturing organizations who made the arrangements for the employees regarding the workplace safety in an organization and minimizes the loss and reduce the accidents and incidents by adopting the safety measures.

Secondly this study is also beneficial for the employees who work in the industries to improve the methods of working. And my study is also helpful for the researchers who want to do further research in this sector or may do further research with different aspects.

This study is focused on the safety of employees who work in the plastic footwear manufacturing industries. This study does not cover any other manufacturing industries.

Literature review

DeJoy, Schaffer, and Wilson (2004) carried out research to explore the significant interest in safety climate and to assess the proposed mediating role of safety climate in relation to safety-related outcomes. Diaz and Diaz-Cabrera (1997) discovered that an organization's safety-related policies were the most significant indicator of its safety climate. These policies encompassed aspects such as adherence to safety standards, provision of safety training, availability of safety resources, and feedback on safety performance. James and James (1989) note that organizational climate generally comprises various individual assessments of the work environment.

Neal, Griffin, and Hart (2000) aimed to investigate how the general organizational climate impacts both the safety climate and safety performance. This study operated under the fundamental premise that the link between safety climate and overall system safety is, to some extent, mediated by individual safety behaviors. They define safety climate as a particular aspect of organizational climate, characterizing it as the individual perceptions regarding the importance of safety within the work environment. Borman and Motowidlo (1993), along with Campbell et al. (1993), outline that the elements of performance encompass the key dimensions of behaviors relevant to a specific job. Their model introduces two dimensions of safety performance: compliance and participation. Safety compliance is about following safety procedures and executing work safely.

Campbell et al. (1993) contend that individual performance differences can be attributed to just three factors: knowledge, skill, and motivation. However, this view has been challenged by various authors who suggest that other factors might also play a role in determining performance. This paper delves into how the general organizational climate affects the safety climate, and in turn, how the safety climate influences individuals' knowledge, motivation, and performance within organizations. Walker and Hutton (2006) undertook a study to explore individuals' beliefs regarding reciprocal safety obligations, which are derived from both implicit and explicit promises. Despite the expanding body of literature on psychological contracts, the specific existence of such contracts in the context of safety had not been clearly established. Their research aimed to uncover the presence of psychological contracts within employee discussions about safety.

Mearns, Whitaker, and Flin (2003) carried out a research project across 13 offshore oil and gas installations over various years. The purpose of this study was to conduct a cross-organizational survey aimed at benchmarking the participating offshore installations in terms of their safety climate, as well as identifying the best practices in safety management.

The notion of 'safety culture' has evolved considerably since the OECD Nuclear Agency's 1987 observation. This agency noted that the mistakes and procedural violations leading up to the Chernobyl disaster were indicative of a deficient safety culture at the plant and, more broadly,

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within the former Soviet nuclear industry. This perspective was further elaborated by Pidgeon and O'Leary in 2000. Cooper and Phillips (2004) undertook a study to investigate how the safety climate affects an organization's overall safety performance. They distributed a measure of safety climate to employees in the manufacturing sector at the start of a behavioral safety initiative, and then redistributed it a year later for comparison.

Research Methodology

Theoretical framework

Plastic footwear manufacturing industries Our study area is plastic footwear manufacturing industries situated at timber market, Ravi road, Lahore.

The population of my study is Plastic footwear manufacturing sector. Convenient sampling techniques is choose, In this study the sample size was 106, the respondent were selected from different plastic footwear manufacturing industries. Questionnaire is a research instrument consisting of series of questions. The questionnaire was invented by Professional training services (PTS) by the bureau of state risk management. A questionnaire is a research instrument consisting of a series of questions and other prompts for the purpose of gathering information from respondents. Although they are often designed for statistical analysis of the responses. The questionnaire was invented by Professional training services (PTS) by the bureau of state risk

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management. Questionnaires have advantages over some other types of surveys like fire safety standards, because they are cheap, do not require as much effort from the questioner as verbal or telephone surveys, and often have standardized answers that make it simple to compile data. However, such standardized answers may frustrate users. Interview when we interview, we are not extracting information like a dentist pulls a tooth, but we make meaning together like two dancers, one leading and one following.

Workplace safety was measure by asking the 12 questions by using the 5-points itemized rating type scale. Job performance was measure by asking the 11 questions by using the 5-points itemized rating type scale.

Data analysis

Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	106	100.0	100.0	100.0

The table represents that total respondents are choose on the basis of gender is 100% male, and total frequency of respondents is 106, cumulative percent is 100 belongs to Male. All the respondents are valid and complete in every respect.

Qualification

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Below Matric	62	58.5	58.5	58.5
Matric	32	30.2	30.2	88.7
Intermediate	10	9.4	9.4	98.1
Others	2	1.9	1.9	100.0
Total	106	100.0	100.0	

The table represents that total sample contains 106 respondents out of which 62 (58.5%) respondents fall in the below matric bracket, frequency of 32 (30.2%) respondents belongs to matric qualification, the 10 (9.4%) respondents fall in the intermediate qualification and 2 (1.9%) respondents belongs to others like diploma in associate engineering.

Age

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 20-29 Years	77	72.6	72.6	72.6
30-39 Years	26	24.5	24.5	97.2
40-49 Years	3	2.8	2.8	100.0
Total	106	100.0	100.0	

The table represents that the demographic variable like age, total respondents 106 out of which 77

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(72.6%) respondents falls in the 20-29 years age bracket, and 26 (24.5%) respondents falls in the 30-39 years age bracket, and remaining 3 (2.8%) respondents belongs to 40-49 years age bracket. All the respondents are valid and complete in every respect.

Reliability

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.654	28

Above table shows the reliability analysis of the whole study. The reliability analysis of this study or cronbach's alpha 0.654 or 65.4% and total number of items are 28.

Correlation

		Average of Workplace safety	Average of job performance
Average of Workplace safety	Pearson Correlation	1	.146
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.134
	N	106	106
Average of job performance	Pearson Correlation	.146	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.134	
	N	106	106

In the above table the correlation between two variables like average of workplace safety and average of job performance. This table shows significant result. Pearson correlations between both variables are 0.146, and number of respondents is 106. So the average of workplace safety depends on the average of workplace safety.

Regression

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.146(a)	.021	.012	.33966

a Predictors: (Constant), Average of Workplace safety

ANOVA (b)

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.263	1	.263	2.275	.134(a)
	Residual	11.999	104	.115		

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Total	12.261	105			
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a Predictors: (Constant), Average of Workplace safety

b Dependent Variable: Average of job performance

The above table shows the regression is 0.263, F is 2.275 and sig is .134. The table shows the significant result. The calculation value does not fall in the critical region so significant result between average of workplace safety and average of job performance. The sum of squares in terms of residual is 11.999, df 104, mean square 0.115. Total sum of squares is 12.261.

Discussion

Workplace safety plays a very important role in the manufacturing industries and in Pakistan. In current stage employers provide safety to the employees for the improvement in working conditions. Plastic footwear industries are facing very tough competition in the footwear industries. There are many competitors of plastic footwear manufacturing sector which offers better quality on low prices.

Footwear manufacturing sector plays a very important role for the development of the economy of the country. In the introduction, we discuss the workplace safety. After all that, discussion gap analysis is also mentioned according to the research problem. It is also shown that how employee's workplace safety influences on the job performance.

Questionnaire is a research instrument contained some basic question was, which are associated with workplace safety and job performance. Questionnaire is divided into two parts, first part was related to demographic information and second part consists of some factors were asked. Factor analysis technique was checked through SPSS 15. Moreover, five point scale was used ranking from strongly agree to strongly disagree. This study related to role of employees workplace safety. Total 106 respondents were selected as sample. 106 questionnaires were received so the response rate was 100%. All demographic information of respondents was tabulated in table.

Conclusion:

The study of role of employee's workplace safety towards job performance on plastic footwear manufacturing industry at timber market, Lahore

Total number of respondents are 106, out of 106 respondents, majority of respondents were below matric, 31% respondents belongs to matric qualification, whereas the remaining were intermediate and above. There is significant result between Average of workplace safety and Average of job performance, so the average of workplace safety depends on the average of job performance.

The results indicate that management show an interest in the safety of their employees depends upon the average of job performance. ($r = .105, \alpha = 0.284$). The regression analysis shows that the relationship between management shows an interest in the safety of their employees and average of job performance ($\beta = .105, \alpha = .284$)

My immediate supervisor show interest in the safety and health of the employees in my area depend upon the average of job performance. ($r = .200, \alpha = .040$) as it regression table shows that there is significant results in view there is relationship between My immediate supervisor show interest in the safety and health of the employees in my area and the average of job performance ($\beta = .200, \alpha = .040$)

The Proper personal protective equipment for my job is always available depend upon the average of job performance. So we conclude that the bivariate correlation and regression show the

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significant results ($r=.008$, $\alpha=.936$) as it regression table shows that there is significant results in view there is relationship between The Proper personal protective equipment for my job is always available and the average of job performance ($\beta =.008$, $\alpha=.936$).

The identified workplace safety concerns are addressed or corrected in a timely manner depend on average of job performance. Regression analysis shows the results that there is relationship between the identified workplace safety concerns are addressed or corrected in a timely manner and average of job performance ($r=.295$, $\alpha=.002$) and ($\beta =.295$, $\alpha=.002$).

The workplace safety rule of this organization have been clearly explained to me not depend on the average of job performance. There is no relationship between the workplace safety rules of this organization have been clearly explained to me and the average of job performance. Regression and correlation shows the insignificant results.

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